

Grain quality attributes of 11 red rice genotypes. Kerala, India, 1989.

Genotype	Brown rice			Milled rice						
	Grain length (mm)	Grain breadth (mm)	L/B ratio	Hulling percentage (% of rough rice)	Milling percentage (% of rough rice)	Alkali spreading value	Water uptake (%)	Amylose content (% dry basis)	Protein content (% dry basis)	Elongation ratio
Bhadra	5.11	2.42	2.11	79.5	73.5	7.0	350	21.1	10.2	1.76
Asha(R)	6.20	2.58	2.40	80.0	73.5	6.0	365	18.9	9.4	1.61
Pavizham	5.32	2.72	1.95	79.5	73.5	3.0	315	16.0	7.5	1.69
Karthika	7.05	2.50	2.82	80.5	74.5	6.0	355	21.2	10.6	1.53
Aruna	5.39	2.55	2.11	74.0	64.5	3.0	240	20.6	9.6	2.23
Makam	5.33	2.31	2.39	79.0	70.0	6.0	260	18.6	9.4	1.62
Remya	6.56	2.60	2.52	75.5	70.0	6.0	320	21.9	10.9	1.92
Kanakam	5.38	2.53	2.13	76.5	68.5	2.0	230	20.6	9.5	1.75
KAU200	5.35	2.54	2.11	79.5	70.5	5.3	320	20.3	9.2	1.79
KAU204	5.32	2.46	2.16	75.0	67.5	5.0	325	20.3	9.4	1.84
KAU168	5.74	2.22	2.58	74.5	67.0	3.0	230	19.4	9.2	1.81

Grain length was 5.11-7.05 mm and length/breadth ratio was 1.95 to 2.82. Water uptake was highest in Asha (R), and lowest in Kanakam and KAU168. Amylose content ranged from 16% in Pavizham to 21.9% in Remya.

Protein content was highest in Remya (10.9% dry basis) and lowest in Pavizham (7.5%). Elongation ratio ranged from 1.53 in Karthika to 2.23 in Aruna. □

an effective, quick way to transfer the resistance gene and obtain stable pollen progenies with BB resistance.

Of 579 H₂ pollen strains of seven combinations, 572 strains (95.5%) were uniform and stable, 62.9% with high or moderate resistance and 32.7% with no resistance. Additionally, 27 heterozygous strains (4.5%) showed segregating resistance (see figure).

The BB resistance of H₂ plants is more significant than that of F₂ plants. For example, in the progenies of Shennong 1033/75-34, lesion area variation is 5-100% in H₂ and 5-45% in F₂. Growth duration and resistance show a significant relationship. BB resistance is higher in strains with longer growth duration.

H₂ strains varied greatly in growth duration, plant height, panicle length, and grain weight. Genetic analysis of results indicated that in the combination, a dominant epistatic gene controlled BB resistance. Broad heritability was more

Pest resistance—diseases

Genetic analysis of bacterial blight (BB) resistance in rice anther culture progenies

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To study BB resistance inheritance in rice anther culture progenies, we crossed susceptible Shennong 1033 (japonica) with resistant varieties: indicas Zenith, 75-35, IR20; and japonicas Wase Aikoku 3, Pei Zhao 15, Bang Zhu Mang, Java 14. F₁ plants of the combinations were used for anther culture. BB resistance was evaluated by the IRRI standard system.

We observed the transfer of the resistance gene in pollen plants (H₂) and resistance stability in H₂, H₃, and H₄. results indicated that anther culture was

BB resistance reaction of anther culture H₂ populations derived from 7 combinations.

than 80%. Many types of pollen strains combined the two parents' traits, with variation ranging close to that of F₂ progenies.

The stability of BB resistance and of other agricultural traits were analyzed in H₃ and H₄ (see table). In pollen plants, these were all relatively stable in different generations. In stable H₂ pollen strains, the resistance capability and character uniformities did not vary with generation advance (H₃ and H₄).

We concluded that the anther culture method effectively transfers the resistance gene. □

Stability of pollen strain resistance to bacterial blight.

Cross	Generation	Strain no.	Lesion area ^a (%)	Strain no.	Lesion area ^b (%)
Shennong 1033/Zenith	H ₂	89-3710	3.0 ± 0.2	89-3724	16.7 ± 1.6
	H ₃		2.0 ± 1.8		16.8 ± 1.4
	H ₄		2.3 ± 0.1		15.7 ± 1.4
Shennong 1033/75-34	H ₂	89-3841	4.7 ± 0.2	89-3873	14.5 ± 0.8
	H ₃		4.7 ± 0.2		14.7 ± 1.2
	H ₄		4.9 ± 0.1		15.7 ± 1.4
Shennong 1033/Java 14	H ₂	89-3753	2.9 ± 0.2	89-3924	14.0 ± 1.3
	H ₃		4.9 ± 0.1		13.3 ± 1.6
	H ₄		4.9 ± 0.1		12.8 ± 1.2
Shennong 1033/Pei Zhao 15	H ₂	89-3795	4.9 ± 0.1	89-3819	14.9 ± 1.1
	H ₃		4.9 ± 0.1		13.9 ± 1.2
	H ₄		4.9 ± 0.1		14.1 ± 1.1

^aAll values are equivalent to R (resistant). ^bAll values are equivalent to MR (moderately resistant).

Resistance to sheath blight (ShB) and brown spot (BS) in lines derived from *Oryza officinalis*

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We evaluated 87 breeding lines derived from *O. officinalis* for resistance to ShB caused by *Thanatephorus cucumeris* (Frank) Donk, and BS caused by *Cochliobolus miyabeanus* (Ito & Kuribayashi) Drechsler ex Dastur.

In the field, one row per line and check TKM9 were transplanted at 30 × 15-cm in 3-m-long plots, in a randomized block with three replications.

We assessed ShB weekly and BS biweekly from active tillering to the milk stage, using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES). Lines completely free from ShB and BS were artificially inoculated for further evaluation.

Disease incidence was evaluated in the greenhouse by stem tape inoculation for ShB and spore suspension spray for BS, on 21 seedlings/line. Actively tillering plants were inoculated with 20-d-old ShB pathogen cultured on autoclaved rice stem pieces, inserted into the sheaths, 5 cm above the water line. For BS inoculation, plants were sprayed with a 10⁷ conidia/ml suspension.

Disease severity was assessed every 7 d for ShB and every 10 d for BS from the

Lines derived from *O. officinalis* showing resistance to ShB and BS.

Intensity (0-9 scale)	Lines	
	ShB	BS
1 (highly resistant)	IR54742-6-1-14-15-3 IR54742-33-18-20-3-2 IR54745-2-10-17-8-3 IR54745-2-23-19-8-2 IR54742-1-11-17-12-3	IR54742-1-11-17-26-1 IR54742-1-17-20-8-3 IR54742-33-9-14-26-4 IR54742-33-18-20-3-1 IR54742-33-18-20-3-2 IR54742-38-13-15-11-1 IR54745-2-10-17-8-1 IR54745-2-21-12-17-4 IR54745-2-23-19-8-1 IR54745-2-23-19-18-2
3 (resistant)	IR54742-1-11-17-12-1 IR54742-1-11-17-12-3 IR54742-1-11-17-26-2 IR54742-6-20-3-9-3 IR54742-11-1-9-15-1 IR54742-33-9-14-26-4 IR54745-2-21-12-17-4 IR54745-2-34-3-10-2 IR54751-3-38-10-15-3 IR54742-50-19-19-1-1 IR54742-50-19-19-1-3	IR54742-1-11-17-12-1 IR54742-1-11-17-12-3 IR54742-1-19-11-8-2 IR54742-6-20-3-22-3 IR54742-6-20-9-3-2 IR54742-11-22-2-22-2 IR54742-18-17-20-15-1 IR54742-22-14-24-22-3 IR54742-22-19-3-7-3 IR54742-31-9-26-15-2 IR54742-33-18-20-3-2 IR54745-2-10-17-8-3 IR54745-2-21-12-17-5 IR54745-2-34-3-10-2
9 (highly susceptible)	TKM9 (check)	TKM9

time symptoms appeared on the susceptible check until the milk stage.

Under natural infection, 87 and 48 of the derived lines were ShB- and BS-free.

Under artificial inoculation, 5 lines were highly resistant to ShB and 10 to BS (see table). □

Resistance to sheath rot (ShR) of breeding lines derived from *Oryza officinalis*

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We evaluated 87 breeding lines derived from *O. officinalis* for resistance to ShR caused by *Sarocladium oryzae* (Sawada) W. Gams & Hawksw.

Twenty plants for each derived line were transplanted into 1-row, 3-m-long plots spaced at 30 × 15 cm. Beds were laid out in randomized blocks with three replications. From booting stage onward,